

Impact of Linear Growth-Improving Interventions on Childhood Overnutrition at 24 Months: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abbreviations:

BMI: Body Mass Index

D₂O: Deuterium Oxide

FFM: Fat-Free Mass

FM: Fat Mass

GLMs: Generalized Linear Models

IFA: Iron and Folic Acid

ICDS: Integrated Child Development Services

IWG: Inadequate Weight Gain

KDE: Kernel Density Estimation

LBW: Low Birth Weight

LMICs: Low- to Middle-Income Countries

Mean Difference: MD

MMN: Multiple Micronutrients

NCDs: Non-Communicable Diseases

NFHS: National Family Health Survey

RCT: Randomized Controlled Trial

SD: Standard Deviation

TBW: Total Body Water

WaSH: Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene

WHO: World Health Organization

WINGS: Women and Infants Integrated Interventions for Growth Study

Abstract

1 **Background:** Childhood malnutrition, both undernutrition and overnutrition, is a major health
2 concern in many lower-and middle-income countries (LMICs). Efforts to reduce early
3 undernutrition could also lead to obesity. In an earlier study, we reported the successful impact
4 of a package of pre-conception, pregnancy, postnatal and/or early childhood interventions
5 (health, nutrition, psychosocial support, and water, sanitation and hygiene, WaSH) delivered in
6 the first 1000 days, on reducing stunting in low-to-middle income populations, in comparison to
7 routine care. However, the impact of these interventions on early body composition and
8 subsequent overweight is not known.

9 **Objective:** To estimate the effect of a package of interventions directed at preventing stunting in
10 the first 1000 days, on body composition at one month and childhood overweight and/or obesity
11 at 24 months of age.

12 **Methods:** Infant body composition was measured by deuterium dilution at one month of age,
13 along with the prevalence of childhood overweight and/or obesity at 24 months, defined by a
14 BMI-for-Age Z (BMIz) score above +2 SD.

15 **Results:** Children in the pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood intervention group and
16 those in the pregnancy and early childhood intervention group, had higher BMIz scores
17 compared to those in routine care. However, the prevalence of overweight and/or obesity was
18 low (ranging from 0.0–1.3%). Pregnancy interventions significantly increased neonatal Fat Free
19 Mass (FFM, mean difference 0.1kg, 95% CI: 0.01, 0.2 kg). However, there was no significant
20 change in Fat Mass.

21 **Conclusions:** Comprehensive interventions from pre-conception to early childhood improves
22 linear growth but do not result in overweight and/or obesity at 24 months. With better resultant

23 linear and ponderal growth, they converge with the WHO “double-duty actions for nutrition” for
24 LMIC settings, where childhood overweight and/or obesity is a growing concern.

25

26 **Clinical Trial Registry number and website where it was obtained** ([CTRI/2017/06/008908](https://www.clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03611111))

27 [Registered on: 23/06/2017]

28 **Keywords:** Childhood Obesity, Community-Based Interventions, Early Childhood

29 Development, Linear Growth, Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), Maternal

30 Environment, Nutritional Supplements, Ponderal Growth, Pre-Conception Interventions,

31 Pregnancy Interventions

32

33 **Introduction**

34 The double burden of malnutrition, characterized by the co-existence of undernutrition and
35 overnutrition, is a growing concern in many low-to middle-income countries (LMICs). It is
36 linked to early life health adversities like low birth weight, underweight and stunting on the one
37 hand, and childhood overweight or obesity on the other, and accordingly, the risk of non-
38 communicable diseases (NCDs) later in life (1, 2). The nutritional and economic transition in
39 many LMICs has shifted childhood nutritional outcomes from mainly undernutrition to the
40 double burden of malnutrition(3). This signifies that countries that previously grappled with
41 widespread undernutrition among children are now facing the additional challenge of overweight
42 and obesity. In 2022, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported over 37 million under-five
43 children were overweight globally, with nearly half in Asia(4). The Indian National Family
44 Health Survey (NFHS) Round 5 data (conducted between 2019-2021) showed a 60% increase in
45 childhood overweight compared to the earlier NFHS-4 conducted five years earlier (5, 6).

46 There is growing evidence that the interventions aimed at stunting prevention may inadvertently
47 increase the risk of childhood overweight and obesity(7, 8). Rapid weight gain in infancy,
48 particularly following early stunting, has been associated with increased adiposity and metabolic
49 risk in later life(9-11). This risk arises from the interconnected biological, environmental, and
50 socioeconomic etiologies contributing to both undernutrition and obesity, highlighting the need
51 for carefully balanced interventions(12).

52 We conducted a community based RCT using a 2x2 factorial design, entitled '*Women and*
53 *Infants Integrated Interventions for Growth Study*' (WINGS) in an urban, low-to-middle income
54 neighborhood of Delhi, that included a package of health, nutrition, psychosocial care, and
55 WaSH interventions delivered during preconception, pregnancy, and early childhood periods (13,

56 14). By focusing on critical periods in early life, these interventions can potentially disrupt the
57 intergenerational transmission of obesity by targeting the vulnerable period of growth. While
58 WINGS was impressively successful in reducing the incidence of low birth weight and stunting
59 at 24 months, one of the predefined secondary outcomes aimed to investigate whether these
60 interventions could also improve early infant body composition and reduce the prevalence of
61 overweight and/or obesity at 24 months of age in children (13).

62

63 **Methods**

64 *Study participants*

65 In the WINGS trial, married females aged 18-30 (n=13,500) residing in a low-to-middle-income
66 neighborhood in South Delhi, were recruited through a house-to-house survey. Recruitment took
67 place between 1 July 2017 and 30 December 2019 and females who had no more than one child
68 were eligible for inclusion and those living in temporary housing were excluded. Females were
69 initially randomized into a preconception intervention group and a routine care group. Upon
70 pregnancy confirmation, a second randomization resulted in four groups: Group A received
71 Preconception care and Enhanced Antenatal, Postnatal, and Early Childhood care. Group B
72 received Preconception care, Routine Antenatal, Postnatal, and Early Childhood care. Group C
73 received the Preconception care, and Enhanced Antenatal, Postnatal, and Early Childhood care.
74 Group D received only Routine Antenatal, Postnatal, and Early Childhood care (**Supplementary**
75 **Figure 1**).

76 *Randomization and Blinding*

77 A computer-based randomization sequence was used, incorporating block randomization
78 stratified by maternal height (<150 cm or \geq 150 cm). The randomization list was generated by a

79 statistician otherwise not involved in the study (14). The allocation was concealed, the study staff
80 did not know the study group until the female had consented to participate. Due to the
81 intervention's nature, participants and care providers were not blinded; however, outcome
82 assessors for anthropometry and body composition measures were blinded to the group identity
83 to minimize bias in outcome assessment.

84 The trial was stopped early following an interim analysis, as recommended by the Data Safety
85 Monitoring Board, due to significant beneficial effects on low birth weight and stunting at 24
86 months. Consequently, the final sample size was smaller than originally planned, with fewer
87 participants than indicated in the protocol(14).

88 Routine Care:

89 Females in the routine care group had access to standard care available through government
90 health programs, such as antenatal and postnatal care, iron and folic acid supplementation, and
91 the provision of supplementary food through the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS)
92 scheme (Refer to **Supplementary Table 1**).

93 Ethical approval for the trial was obtained from the Ethics Review Committee of the Society for
94 Applied Studies, New Delhi (SAS/ERC/LG/2017), Vardhman Medical College and Safdarjung
95 Hospital, New Delhi (IEC/SJH/VMMC/PROJECT-2017/694) and the World Health
96 Organization, Geneva (ERC.0002934). This analysis was also approved by Regional Committees
97 for Medical and Health Research Ethics, Norway (REK Number 511978). Written informed
98 consent was provided by caregivers.

99 *Study Interventions*

100 The interventions, encompassing health, nutrition, WaSH and psychosocial care and support,
101 were delivered across pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood (up to 24 months), as

102 reported earlier(13). Follow-up for child growth and development continued until the final
103 assessment at 24 months, which was completed by June 2021. In brief, the preconception
104 intervention included medical screenings and supplements, with additional food supplements for
105 those with a BMI below 21 kg/m², and hygiene counseling. Three Monthly follow-ups were
106 conducted to monitor health, identify missed periods, and provide interventions such as
107 nutritional supplementation and health education. During pregnancy, antenatal care, medical
108 screenings, and daily supplements were provided, and those with a BMI below 25 kg/m² in later
109 pregnancy received food supplements. Families were equipped with hygiene facilities and
110 received sanitation guidance. Females were counseled on positive thinking and problem-
111 solving(15). Once pregnant, females attended antenatal visits to monitor maternal health and
112 fetal growth, and monthly visits by worker to provide micronutrient supplementation and
113 nutritional counseling at home. Weight of pregnant females was monitored every month and
114 inadequate weight gain was identified according to Institute of Medicine guidelines(16).
115 Newborns were visited at home within 24 hours of birth or hospital discharge, followed by five
116 visits in the first month, monthly visits until 12 months, and every three months thereafter until
117 24 months. Additional visits were made for lactation difficulties or growth failure, which was a
118 key part of the intervention's nature. In the first six postpartum months , daily iron and folic acid
119 (IFA), multiple micronutrients, calcium, vitamin D supplements, and food supplements that
120 provided an additional 600 kcal of energy and 20g protein, were provided(17). Infants received
121 daily vitamin D and IFA supplements, with the latter starting from 2 weeks for very-low-
122 birthweight infants and 6 weeks for low-birthweight infants. Children aged 6-24 months received
123 daily IFA, a fortified milk-cereal mix (125 Kcal, 2.6 g protein), and 6-monthly deworming

124 tablets. Children over 6 months of age with inadequate weight gain received medical treatment
125 and additional food supplements (Refer to Supplementary Table 2 for more details).

126 *Measurements*

127 For anthropometric measurements, we adhered to the protocol as outlined by the World Health
128 Organization (WHO) Multicenter Growth Reference Study(18). Child's weight and length were
129 independently measured by two workers using standardized equipment within the first week of
130 birth, at one month, and three monthly thereafter until 24 months of age. If the discrepancy
131 between their measurements exceeded the pre-specified limits (7 mm for length and 10 g for
132 weight), the measurements were repeated for accuracy.

133 In a randomly selected subsample of 600 participants, body composition was evaluated at one
134 month of age, using a two-compartment body model to measure the Fat-Free Mass (FFM), Fat
135 Mass (FM) and percentage Fat Mass (% FM). To do so, a dose of deuterium oxide (D₂O, 99.8%,
136 Sercon International, UK; 0.2 g/kg infant body weight) was administered to measure the Total
137 Body Water (TBW) by measurement of the deuterium dilution space(19). The D₂O was weighed
138 to the nearest 0.01g, diluted in an equal amount of water and orally administered after the
139 collection of pre-dosing saliva samples. Two post-dose saliva samples were collected after a 3-
140 hour equilibration period and stored in a cool box (2-8°C) for transport to the central lab, where
141 they were transferred to a -80°C freezer until further analysis. For each assessment of TBW, the
142 enrichment of D₂O was measured in duplicate, in post-dose saliva samples, using Fourier-
143 Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometry at St. John's Research Institute, Bangalore, India. The
144 enrichment of the diluted dose was also measured for each infant.

145 For the D₂O analysis, the limit of detection (LOD) was 0.02% deuterium enrichment, and the limit
146 of quantification (LOQ) was 0.05%. The natural abundance of deuterium in body water (~0.015

147 atom %) was measured using FTIR Spectroscopy. After administering a known amount of D₂O,
148 the postdose enrichment (postdose - predose) was calculated and used for body composition
149 measurements.

150 The FTIR was calibrated using a standard curve (0–1000 ppm excess enrichment) at the start of
151 each assay, with daily calibration checks using 0 and 1000 enrichment standards. Intra-assay CVs
152 were <2% and <1%, and inter-assay CVs were <1%, ensuring precision. Data below the LOD were
153 excluded, and those between the LOD and LOQ were reviewed and removed if they affected
154 outcomes. All data above the LOQ were retained for analysis.

155 The deuterium dilution space, calculated as the ratio of the dose of D₂O administered to the
156 deuterium enrichment of post-dose saliva samples, was converted to TBW using a factor of
157 1.041 to adjust for proton exchange (20). The FFM was then calculated from the TBW, as its
158 ratio to FFM age- and sex-specific hydration coefficients [FFM = TBW / 0.80] (21, 22). FM was
159 determined by subtracting the FFM from the body weight. The data were inspected for
160 implausible values, predicated on the FM values falling below the -0.1 threshold, a criterion set
161 to accommodate the inherent technical variability in deuterium measurements. Values that were
162 deemed implausible were excluded from the analysis.

163 *Statistical analyses*

164 We conducted analyses for three predefined comparisons: Groups receiving pre-conception care
165 intervention (Group A+B) were compared with groups not receiving pre-conception care
166 intervention (Group C+D). Groups receiving intervention during pregnancy and early childhood
167 (Group A+C) were compared with groups receiving routine care during these periods (B+D).
168 Finally, groups receiving intervention during pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood
169 (Group A) were compared with the control group (Group D).

170 For childhood overweight and/or obesity at 24 months, the outcome variable studied was BMIz
171 (serves as a proxy for ponderal growth, defined as the weight gain relative to height), with a
172 score above +2 SD, calculated using age- and sex-specific reference data from the WHO 2006
173 growth standards (18). Linear growth refers to the increase in stature, measured through length-
174 for-age Z-scores, assessing how tall a child grows over time. Following an interim analysis at
175 50% of the sample size achieved for the 24-month outcomes, the Data Safety and Monitoring
176 Committee (DSMC) recommended halting the study due to clear evidence of beneficial effects,
177 based on the prespecified stopping rule at $P < 0.001$ (14). The original sample size calculation
178 was designed to detect differences in low birth weight and stunting, and BMIz-score was not a
179 primary outcome. Given the early stopping, the final sample size was smaller than initially
180 planned. Consequently, the BMIz-score analysis was conducted post-hoc, with power
181 calculations based on the achieved sample size. The sample size for body composition was pre-
182 calculated to detect a 0.4 SD difference in fat mass between Group A (full package) and Group D
183 (standard care), corresponding to a 100 g difference at 28 days of life, with 90% power and a 5%
184 significance level (23). This required 131 children per group, and assuming 15% refusal we
185 aimed to recruit 150 per group. For the comparison between Groups A+B and C+D, the study
186 was powered to detect a 0.27 SD difference (67.5 g) with 90% power.

187 BMIz scores were calculated using the STATA module *zanthro* (24). To investigate the impact
188 of the interventions, we analyzed BMIz at 24 months using Generalized Linear Models (GLMs)
189 specified with the Gaussian family and an identity link function. The models included maternal
190 preconceptional BMI as a covariate, given its association with child growth and
191 development (16). The models were executed as pre-decided at a confidence level of 98.3% to
192 account for multiple comparisons, with 98.3% confidence intervals used for all outcomes to

193 adjust for the three comparisons (significance level 0.017 or 0.05/3) and standard errors were
194 calculated after accounting for clustering due to twins at the household level(14). Graphical
195 comparisons were also conducted to visualize the distribution of BMIZ scores across different
196 groups. The kernel density estimation (KDE) was used to generate these plots. The KDE plots
197 were generated for BMIZ scores greater than or equal to -5.0 and for those individuals who were
198 included in the 24-month analysis. In addition to the comparisons of BMIZ scores at 24 months,
199 BMIZ score trajectories from birth to 24 months were charted at 3-month intervals. Mixed-effects
200 models estimated predicted BMIZ-scores, with group and time as fixed effects, and an
201 interaction term to assess differences across groups. Child identity was included as a random
202 effect to account for within-child correlations from repeated measurements. We used GLM with
203 Gaussian family and an identity link function to investigate the impact of interventions on body
204 composition parameters for all three comparisons given the continuous nature of the variables
205 (FFM, FM and % body fat). Due to field challenges, such as delays in sample collection, body
206 composition data for FFM, FM, and %FM were missing in 182 cases. We assumed a Missing at
207 Random (MAR) mechanism, where the likelihood of missingness depends on observed data
208 rather than unobserved data (25). To handle this, we performed multiple imputation by chained
209 equations (MICE) using 20 imputed datasets(26). Both imputed results and complete-case
210 analyses are presented side by side in the results to demonstrate robustness across methods. For
211 detailed information on the missing data analysis procedures, please refer to the Supplementary
212 Information on Missing Data Handling. All analyses were conducted using STATA v16.1
213 (StataCorp).

214

215 **Results**

216 From July 2017 to December 2019, 13,500 eligible females were enrolled in the study. After the
217 second randomization, the number of live births was 1,290 in Group A, 1,276 in Group B, 1,093
218 in Group C, and 1,093 in Group D. A detailed participant flow is illustrated in **Figure 1**, which
219 shows the recruitment, randomization, and follow-up processes, including reasons for exclusions
220 and losses to follow-up.

221 The trial was stopped early on 30 June 2021, due to observed beneficial effects ($p < 0.001$) on the
222 primary outcomes related to low birth weight and stunting at 24 months of age, per interim
223 analyses. Children who were 24 months old by this stop date of 30 June 2021 were included in
224 this analysis. This included 453 in group A, 439 in group B, 293 in group C, and 271 in group
225 D. The baseline characteristics are presented in Table 1. There were no substantial differences
226 across the groups except for maternal BMI, possession of a below-poverty-line card, and place of
227 birth. In the GLM Model, only pre-conceptional BMI was included as an adjustment variable.

228 The proportion of children with overweight and/or obesity at 24 months, across the different
229 groups, was very low: Group A: 6 (1.3%), Group B: 2 (0.5%), Group C: 3 (1.0%), and Group D:
230 none. These proportions were not significantly different between groups ($P = 0.185$). The
231 adjusted BMIz scores at 24 months between the groups A+C and B+D was 0.33 (98.3% CI: 0.1,
232 0.5), while the difference between group A and D was also 0.33 (98.3% CI: 0.1, 0.5), indicating
233 a modest but significant effect of the interventions (**Table 2**). BMIz trajectories between birth
234 and 24 months as shown in **Figure 2**, show a pronounced effect in the groups that received
235 interventions during pregnancy and early childhood (Groups A+C and B+D), as well as in
236 preconception, pregnancy and early childhood, compared to the routine care groups (Groups A
237 and D). As seen in **Supplementary Figure 2**, there was a rightward shift in both tails of the
238 BMIz score distribution, signifying improved BMI in intervention group children while also

239 reducing undernourishment. Notably, this effect was minimal in the group that received pre-
240 conception care intervention compared to those that did not (Group A+B Vs C+D).

241 We also assessed the interaction between preconception and pregnancy/early childhood
242 interventions for BMIz-scores at 24 months of age. There was no significant evidence of
243 interaction ($p = 0.836$) between these two intervention phases, as shown in **Supplementary**
244 **Table 3**. This indicates that the effects of the preconception interventions on BMIz -scores were
245 independent of the pregnancy and early childhood interventions.

246 The descriptive statistics of body composition parameters for each group are presented in
247 Supplementary Table 4. Table 3 shows both imputed and complete-case estimates of body
248 composition analysis. Imputed results were consistent with those of the complete-case analysis.
249 Interventions in pregnancy and early childhood significantly increased infant FFM at one month
250 by 0.11 kg (98.3% CI: 0.02, 0.19) without significant changes in Fat Mass (FM: -0.02 kg; 98.3%
251 CI: -0.01, 0.05) or % FM (-0.4%; 98.3% CI: -1.53, 0.72).

252

253 **Discussion**

254 In these analyses, we evaluated the impact of community-based interventions from pre-
255 conception to early childhood on childhood overweight and/or obesity at 24 months of age, given
256 the previously demonstrated improvement in linear growth(13). These interventions promoted
257 linear growth, without a significant increase in the prevalence of overweight and / or obesity at
258 24 months, suggesting their potential role in influencing children's ponderal growth from birth to
259 24 months of age. The effects were evident in groups receiving interventions during pregnancy,
260 early childhood, and combined pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood. Additionally,

261 pregnancy interventions had a positive impact on body composition, notably leading to a 0.11 kg
262 increase in FFM.

263 These follow-up studies are important, since aggressive feeding interventions can inappropriately
264 increase FM or BMIz scores at young ages, and early-life obesity has been associated with an
265 increased risk of NCDs in adulthood (27, 28). Therefore, interventions aimed at promoting
266 healthy growth in children should be rational, to reduce growth faltering without exacerbating
267 the risk of childhood overweight and/or obesity. Given the multifaceted etiology of childhood
268 malnutrition, interventions must be comprehensive, addressing the root causes of undernutrition
269 from pregnancy through early childhood to support optimal growth and development(29)(30).
270 Improved maternal nutrition during pregnancy will optimize placental function and fetal nutrient
271 transfer, leading to healthier birth weights(31). The interventions in this trial, including
272 preconception and pregnancy nutrition, lactation support, and enhanced complementary feeding,
273 were designed to promote healthy growth rather than prevent obesity. Evidence shows that these
274 strategies improve growth trajectories by addressing nutrient gaps and supporting balanced
275 weight gain without excessive adiposity (32, 33). Responsive care giving practices like optimal
276 feeding, sleep, and interactive play, also foster a positive environment for development (34).
277 However, comprehensive data from LMICs are limited. A pre-conception micronutrient study in
278 Mumbai, India, showed minimal impact on body composition or cardiometabolic risk markers at
279 5 to 8 years, suggesting single interventions may be less effective than multifaceted
280 approaches(35).

281 Our results show that children in the pregnancy and early childhood intervention group had
282 higher BMIz scores but did not have overweight and/or obesity. This challenges the notion that
283 early nutritional supplements make a child overweight or “more adipose.” The WHO’s “double-

284 duty actions for nutrition” addresses both obesity and undernutrition, which is influenced by
285 various factors that shape early life growth patterns(12). By targeting these factors, our package
286 of interventions aimed for healthy and balanced growth, which is vital for the double-duty
287 actions for undernourished populations.

288 Numerous studies have investigated the effects of pregnancy interventions on neonatal body
289 composition. Behavioral and lifestyle interventions to prevent excess weight gain in pregnancy
290 showed no substantial difference in newborn body fat, but a gain in FFM (0.1 ± 0.05 kg; $P =$
291 0.03)(36). A six-month pregnancy mobile-phone app, with a healthy diet and activity program
292 did not significantly alter infant body fat two weeks postpartum (37). A meta-analysis showed no
293 effect of lifestyle interventions during pregnancy on neonatal adiposity [MD: -0.21% , 95% CI ($-$
294 0.92 to 0.50)](38). These studies, primarily from high-income settings suggest that in utero
295 exposures may not affect child's adiposity at birth. These findings, primarily from high-income
296 settings, suggest limited impact of *in utero* exposures on the child's adiposity, possibly due to the
297 already high natural adiposity (10-13%) and body hydration (80%) in human newborns (39-41).
298 Our interventions improved FFM without increasing FM, aligning with these findings. This
299 modest improvement in early-life body composition is notable, as it may contribute to long-term
300 cardiovascular benefits(42, 43). The mechanism of this improvement in FFM at birth by
301 pregnancy interventions that include improved maternal nutrition, control of morbidities, and
302 enhanced psychosocial status, is likely through their influence on the maternal metabolic
303 environment and utero-placental blood flow(44-46).

304 Given the escalating double burden of malnutrition in LMICs, prioritizing the implementation of
305 early life interventions is important. Across all three intervention groups—despite receiving
306 interventions at different stages during the first 1000 days—children exhibited growth

307 trajectories that closely followed WHO BMIz standards up to 24 months(18). This similarity
308 suggests that the interventions did not significantly alter the natural growth pattern but provided
309 slight improvements compared to the control group. These improvements, while small, are still
310 substantial and sustainable for health in the long term, as they can be protective against later
311 NCDs while simultaneously improving length-for-age, and not causing an increase in overweight
312 at 2 years. These findings validate current practices and suggest the potential of comprehensive
313 interventions for preventing excessive weight gain, while supporting sustainable growth patterns.
314 We had 90% power to detect a difference of 0.2 SD in BMIz score between groups at a 5%
315 significance level for each of the three group comparisons (Group A+B vs C+D, Group A+C vs
316 B+D, and Group A vs D). Although BMIz score was not the original primary outcome, this
317 detectable effect size was selected based on clinical relevance observed in other studies, where
318 even a modest change in BMIz score (approximately 0.2-0.3 units) is associated with meaningful
319 improvements in growth trajectories without increasing the risk of obesity (47).

320 Studies in LMICs have shown that even small positive changes (≥ 0) in BMIz score contribute to
321 reduced stunting and improved growth trajectories, which are critical outcomes in these settings
322 (47). The observed 0.3-unit increase in BMIz score is clinically meaningful for promoting healthy
323 growth while avoiding excessive adiposity, supporting public health objectives in LMICs where
324 undernutrition is a greater concern than early-life obesity (12).

325 The present study has several strengths, including a meticulous design, longitudinal data, high
326 adherence to most interventions, standardized anthropometric measurements, and applicability to
327 urban populations with low to middle incomes. However, certain limitations warrant attention.
328 The generalizability of our findings may be influenced by the low prevalence of overweight and
329 obesity, compared to National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) for Indian children under five

330 years of age (6). Additionally, certain risk factors for infant overweight, such as maternal
331 obesity, were relatively uncommon in our sample, which may further limit the applicability of
332 our findings to populations with higher rates of maternal overweight. These factors should be
333 taken into account when interpreting the results and considering the potential impact of similar
334 interventions in other settings. Although the pre-conception intervention was not intended to
335 promote pregnancy, improvements in maternal health may have indirectly influenced fertility,
336 leading to an imbalance in pregnancy rates between groups. This may have affected the sample
337 size available for the 24-month analysis. We were unable to conduct a body composition
338 assessment at 24 months of age. While we acknowledge that missing data may reduce the
339 estimate precision, the consistent trends observed between the imputed and non-imputed datasets
340 suggest that the impact of missingness on our overall conclusions is minimal. Additionally, any
341 trends in missingness did not seem to differ substantially across the intervention groups, further
342 supporting the robustness of our findings.

343 In conclusion, our study suggests that community-based interventions specifically from
344 pregnancy to early childhood, may support linear growth as well as children's healthy ponderal
345 growth up to 2 years, without raising overweight or obesity risk. These interventions align with
346 the WHO's "double-duty actions of nutrition" strategy, which concurrently addresses
347 undernutrition and overweight issues. This is particularly relevant in low-to-middle-income
348 settings such as India.

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353 formal data analysis, and wrote the initial draft. ST, NB and RC conducted the primary trial,
354 designed the experiments, reviewed the data analysis, and contributed to the manuscript. NB
355 supervised the project, provided critical feedback, and contributed to the manuscript. TS
356 conceptualized the manuscript, contributed to formal data analysis, and reviewed the manuscript.
357 SD and PD conducted the body composition analysis. AK contributed to body composition
358 analysis and manuscript writing; and all authors: read and approved the final manuscript. The
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361 **Data Sharing:** The organization conducting the trial (Society for Applied Studies, India) is a
362 collaborator in the Healthy Birth, Growth, and Development Knowledge Integration (HBGDki)
363 of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and the data generated from the study will be shared as
364 part of the HBGDKi repository ([http s://github.com/HBGDKi](http://github.com/HBGDKi)). Individual requests will also be
365 considered on a case-to-case basis. The request for data should be accompanied by a detailed
366 proposal describing the scientific questions to be addressed. Proposals should be submitted to ST
367 (sunita.taneja@sas.org.in).

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Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population post second randomization (included in the analysis)

	Pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood interventions (group A, n=453)	Pre-conception interventions only (group B, n=439)	Pregnancy and early childhood interventions only (group C, n=293)	Control (group D, n=271)
Age of females (years), mean (SD)	23.8 (2.9)	23.8 (2.9)	23.7 (3.0)	23.9 (3.0)
Height <150 (cm), n (%)	153 (33.8)	156 (35.5)	103 (34.8)	94 (34.7)
Maternal Body mass index, kg/m ² . n (%)				
≥25	110 (31.7)	100 (28.8)	61 (17.6)	76 (21.9)
≥ 18.5 & < 25	257 (29.4)	272 (31.2)	190 (21.8)	154 (17.6)
<18.5	86 (36.4)	67 (28.4)	42 (17.8)	41 (17.4)
Joint or extended family ¹ , n (%)	319 (70.4)	307 (69.9)	204 (69.6)	178 (65.7)
Female schooling ≥12 years, n (%)	209 (46.1)	200 (45.6)	139 (47.4)	126 (46.5)
Homemaker, n (%)	428 (94.5)	415 (94.5)	283 (96.6)	260 (95.9)

Family has below poverty line card, n (%)	8 (1.8)	14 (3.2)	14 (4.8)	18 (6.6)
Family covered by health insurance scheme, n (%)	44 (9.7)	39 (8.9)	47 (16)	49 (18.1)
Parity, n (%)				
0	209 (46.1)	183 (41.7)	129 (44.0)	109 (40.2)
1	244 (53.9)	256 (58.3)	164 (56.0)	162 (59.8)
Place of birth, n (%)				
Large hospital	380 (83.9)	241 (54.9)	252 (86.0)	168 (62.0)
Small hospital or birthing centre	63 (13.9)	154 (35.1)	34 (11.6)	84 (31.0)
Home birth	9 (2.0)	43 (9.8)	7 (2.4)	19 (7.0)

SD: Standard Deviation

¹ Joint or extended family: adult relatives other than enrolled female's husband and children living together in household.

Table 2. Crude and adjusted effects [with 98.3% Confidence Interval] of interventions on BMIz score at 24 months of age

Outcomes	Group A (n=453)	Group B (n=439)	Group C (n=293)	Group D (n=271)	Pre-conception intervention vs no pre-conception intervention (Group A + B vs C + D)		Pregnancy intervention vs no pregnancy intervention (Group A + C vs B + D)		Pre-conception and pregnancy intervention vs no pre-conception and pregnancy intervention (Group A vs D)	
					Unadjusted B coeff ¹	Adjusted B coeff ²	Unadjusted B coeff ¹	Adjusted B coeff ²	Unadjusted B coeff ¹	Adjusted B coeff ²
BMIz Score	-0.7 (1.1)	-1.0 (1.0)	-0.8 (1.1)	-1.0 (1.04)	0.04 (-0.1, 0.2)	0.04 (-0.1, 0.2)	0.3(0.1, 0.4)	0.3(0.1, 0.4)	0.3 (0.1, 0.5)	0.3 (0.1, 0.5)

BMI – Body Mass Index

1 Analysis using Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with Gaussian family, identity link

2 Analysis using GLM with Gaussian family, identity link; adjusted for preconceptional BMI.

Group A: preconception, pregnancy and early childhood intervention; group B: only preconception intervention; group C: only pregnancy and early childhood intervention; group D: control.

Group A+B v group C+D: effect of preconception interventions: females who received interventions compared with those who did not receive preconception interventions; group A+C v group B+D: effect of pregnancy and early childhood interventions: females who received these interventions compared with those who did not receive these interventions; group A v group D: effect of preconception, pregnancy, and early childhood interventions: females who received interventions in these periods compared with those who received routine care.

Table 3. Crude and adjusted effects [with 98.3% Confidence Interval] of interventions on body composition parameters at one month of age

Parameter	A+B vs C+D				A+C vs B+D				A Vs D			
	Complete Case ¹ (N=418) (MD, 95% CI)		Imputation Analysis ² (N=600) (MD, 95% CI)		Complete Case (N=418) (MD, 95% CI)		Imputation Analysis (N=600) (MD, 95% CI)		Complete Case (N=418) (MD, 95% CI)		Imputation Analysis (N=600) (MD, 95% CI)	
	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³	Unadjusted	Adjusted ³
Fat-Free Mass (kg)	0.01 (-0.09, 0.12)	0.02 (-0.09, 0.12)	0.04 [-0.05, 0.12]	0.04 [-0.05, 0.12]	0.10 (0.01, 0.2)	0.10 (0.01, 0.2)	0.10 [0.02, 0.19]	0.11 [0.02, 0.19]	0.11 (-0.04, 0.26)	0.12 (-0.04, 0.27)	0.12 [-0.01, 0.24]	0.12 [-0.01, 0.24]
Fat Mass (kg)	-0.01 (-0.07, 0.05)	-0.01 (-0.07, 0.05)	-0.01 [-0.04, 0.05]	-0.01 [-0.05, 0.05]	-0.01 (-0.07, 0.05)	-0.01 (-0.07, 0.05)	-0.02 [-0.05, 0.05]	-0.02 [-0.05, 0.05]	-0.01 (-0.10, 0.07)	-0.01 (-0.09, 0.09)	-0.02 [-0.07, 0.07]	-0.05 [-0.07, 0.07]
% Fat Mass	-0.19 (-1.59, 1.19)	-0.20 (-1.6, 1.1)	-0.11 [-1.23, 1.02]	-0.11 [-1.23, 1.02]	-0.50 (-2.0, 0.8)	-0.60 (-2.0, 0.79)	-0.41 [-1.53, 0.72]	-0.40 [-1.53, 0.72]	-0.73 (-2.8, 1.34)	-0.54 (-2.67, 1.59)	-0.44 [-2.03, 1.13]	-0.38 [-1.96, 1.20]

MD: Mean Difference

1. Analysis performed on complete cases without imputation (N=418) and on a sample with multiple imputation (N=600) for missing data where applicable.

2. Imputed values were generated using multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE) with 20 datasets, followed by pooled estimates using Rubin's rules.

3 Analysis using Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with Gaussian family, identity link, adjusted for preconceptional BMI.

Group A: preconception, pregnancy and early childhood intervention; group B: only preconception intervention; group C: only pregnancy and early childhood intervention; group D: control. Group A+B v group C+D: effect of preconception interventions: females who received interventions compared with those who did not receive preconception interventions; group A+C v group B+D: effect of pregnancy and early childhood interventions: females who received these interventions compared with those who did not receive these interventions; group A v group D: effect of preconception, pregnancy, and early childhood interventions: females who received interventions in these periods compared with those who received routine care.

Figure Legend

Figure 1: Trial Profile

Figure 2: Comparison of BMIz Score trajectories from Birth to 24 Months

BMIz (Body Mass Index Z score)

- A) Groups receiving pre-conception care intervention compared with groups not receiving pre-conception care intervention.
- B) Groups receiving intervention during pregnancy and early childhood compared with groups receiving routine care during these periods.
- C) Groups receiving intervention during pre-conception, pregnancy, and early childhood compared with the control group.

*9 twins, †11 twins, ‡10 twins, §6 twins

Supplementary Figure 1: Flowchart of Randomization and Intervention Allocation in the WINGS Study

Supplementary Table 1. Control Group: National Programs for women of reproductive age, pregnant women and under-twos

The control group had access to services provided by Accredited Social Health Activists (<https://nhm.gov.in/index1.php?lang=1&level=1&sublinkid=150&lid=226>), Integrated Child Development Services (<http://www.wcdde.in/icds.html>), Municipal Corporation of Delhi (MCD) Health Centers, hospitals and private health care practitioners in and around the study areas:

Interventions	National Programs	Access from
Preconception period		
Family planning services including promotion of spacing methods	Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child, and Adolescent Health (https://nhm.gov.in/images/pdf/RM+NCH+A/RMNCH+A_Strategy.pdf), Mission <i>Parivar Vikas</i> (https://main.mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/06Chapter.pdf)	Community health workers called Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs), Maternity & Child Welfare Centres, Family Planning Units in government and private health facilities
Weekly iron-folic acid supplementation	Anemia <i>Mukt Bharat</i> (https://anemiamukt Bharat.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Anemia-Mukt-Bharat-Brochure_English.pdf)	<i>Anganwadi</i> centres, government dispensaries
Pregnancy period		
Early registration of pregnancy, four antenatal care check-ups, institutional delivery	My Safe Motherhood (https://nhm.gov.in/images/pdf/programmes/maternal-health/guidelines/my_safe_motherhood_booklet_english.pdf)	Public and private health facilities
Daily iron-folic acid supplementation for 180 days	Anemia <i>Mukt Bharat</i> (https://anemiamukt Bharat.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Anemia-Mukt-Bharat-Brochure_English.pdf)	<i>Anganwadi</i> centres, government dispensaries, government and private health facilities
Daily calcium and vitamin D supplementation for 180 days	National Guidelines for Calcium Supplementation During Pregnancy and Lactation (http://www.nrhmhp.gov.in/sites/default/files/files/NG_calcium.pdf)	<i>Anganwadi</i> centres, government dispensaries, government and private health facilities
Single dose of tablet Albendazole (400 mg) after 1st trimester		<i>Anganwadi</i> centres, government dispensaries, government and private health facilities
Supplementary food for mothers, either cooked food or take-home ration (600 calories, 18-20 g of protein)	Integrated Child Development Services (http://www.wcdde.in/icds.html)	<i>Anganwadi</i> centres
Postnatal period		

Supplementary food for mothers, either cooked food or take-home ration (600 calories, 18-20 g of protein)	Integrated Child Development Services (http://www.wcdde.in/icds.html)	Anganwadi centres
Daily iron-folic acid supplementation for 180 days	Anemia Mukh Bharat (https://anemiamukhbharat.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Anemia-Mukh-Bharat-Brochure_English.pdf)	Anganwadi centres, government dispensaries, government and private health facilities
Daily calcium and vitamin D supplementation for 180 days	National Guidelines for Calcium Supplementation During Pregnancy and Lactation (http://www.nrhmhp.gov.in/sites/default/files/files/NG_calcium.pdf)	Anganwadi centres, government dispensaries, government and private health facilities
Interventions	National Programs	Access from
Postnatal health checkup	My Safe Motherhood (https://nhm.gov.in/images/pdf/programmes/maternal-health/guidelines/my_safe_motherhood_booklet_english.pdf)	Public and private health facilities where the woman has had her delivery
Postnatal period for children		
Promotion of optimal breastfeeding practices (early initiation of breastfeeding within one-hour, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months, and continued breastfeeding for at least two years)	Mother's Absolute Affection – MAA (https://nhm.gov.in/MAA/Operational_Guidelines.pdf)	Home visits by ASHAs and Anganwadi workers
Home visits for newborn care (days 3, 7, 14, 21, 28 and 42; additionally, on day 1 for home births)	Home Based Newborn Care (http://www.nihfw.org/Doc/NCHRC-Publications/Operational%20Guidelines%20on%20Home%20Based%20Newborn%20Care%20%28HBNC%29.pdf)	ASHAs
Supplementary food (6 to 72 months of age): 500 calories, 12-15 g of protein. For children with severe acute malnutrition, supplementary food increased to 800 calories, 20-25 g of protein	Integrated Child Development Services (http://www.wcdde.in/icds.html)	Anganwadi centres

Impact of Linear Growth-Improving Interventions on Childhood Overweight and Obesity at 24 Months:
 A Randomized Controlled Trial
 Rukman Manapurath

<p>Immunization</p>	<p>Universal Immunization program (https://main.mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/5628564789562315.pdf) based on national immunization schedule (https://nhm.gov.in/New_Updates_2018/NHM_Components/Immunization/report/National %20Immunization Schedule.pdf)</p>	<p>Government dispensaries, public and private health facilities</p>
<p>IFA supplementation from 6 months to 24 months</p>	<p>Anemia <i>Mukt Bharat</i> (https://anemiamukt Bharat.info/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/Anemia-Mukt-Bharat-Brochure_English.pdf)</p>	<p><i>Anganwadi</i> centres, government dispensaries, private practitioners, public and private health facilities</p>
<p>Care for pneumonia and diarrhea among children Integrated Action Plan for Pneumonia and Diarrhea</p>	<p>SAANS initiative (https://nhm.gov.in/index1.php?lang=1&level=4&sublinkid=1336&lid=716)</p>	<p>Government dispensaries, public and private health facilities</p>

Supplementary Table 2: Study Interventions

PRECONCEPTION PERIOD

Intervention	Control†
<p>HEALTH Screen and treat medical conditions known to affect fetal and infant growth i.e. reproductive tract infections, syndromic approach (RTI), symptoms of tuberculosis (TB), hypertension, diabetes (HbA1c \geq6.5%) and pre-diabetes (HbA1c 5.7%-6.4%),hypo-thyroidism (thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) $>$5.5 mIU/ml or TSH 4.01 to 5.5 mIU/l and anti-TPO Ab positive) and hyper-thyroidism ($<$0.4 mIU/ml) Provision of contraception to women living with husband for $<$1 year, having a child aged $<$1 year, severe malnutrition, moderate to severe anemia, hypothyroidism, RTI/STI and diabetes, hypertension Bi-annual deworming (Albendazole 400 mg)</p>	<p>Weekly IFA supplementations as part of the National Iron plus Initiative Program</p>
<p>NUTRITION Weekly iron-folic acid (IFA) supplementation (300 mg ferrous fumerate, 1.5 mgfolic acid, 15 mcg cyanocobalamin) Multiple micronutrients thrice weekly* Screening for malnutrition and anemia Management of undernutrition - BMI $<$16 kg/m²: Refer to hospital, locally-prepared snacks and egg or milk†(1000 kcal/day and 20-22 g protein/day) - BMI 16 to 18.49 kg/m²: Snacks and egg or milk† (500 kcal/day and 12-14 gprotein/day) - BMI $<$18.5 to 20.99 kg/m²: Egg or milk† (70 kcal, 6 g protein) 6 days a week Monthly weight assessment for those with BMI $<$18.5 kg/m²: nutrition counselling and management of infections for those with inadequate weightgain (IWG, weight gain $<$500 g per month) Anemia - Severe anemia (hemoglobin $<$8 g/dL): Refer to hospital for treatment - Mild to moderate anemia (hemoglobin 8 to 11.99 g/dL): treatment with IFA(300 mg ferrous fumerate, 1.5 mg folic acid, 15 mcg cyanocobalamin)</p>	
<p>WaSH Promotion of personal, menstrual and hand hygiene</p>	
<p>PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT Screen for depressive symptoms (using PHQ-9). Counselling by study psychologist if PHQ score \geq 10. Referral to psychiatrist if PHQ-9score \geq 15 and/or presence of suicidal ideation. Promotion of positive thinking and problem-solving skills Screen for substance abuse and exposure to second-hand smoke and alcohol use inhusbands and counsel</p>	

*Composition given at the end

†Observed intake

Monitor above interventions every three months until corrected or pregnancy reported., Repeat investigations done at baseline and for those non-pregnant 12 months post-enrollment.

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PREGNANCY

Intervention Group	Control Group [‡]
<p>HEALTH</p> <p>At least eight antenatal care (ANC) contacts according to WHO ANC guidelines, registration for institutional delivery</p> <p>In addition to hospital-based ANC clinics, increase coverage through free-of-cost, high-quality, study outpatient clinic services within community including laboratory services.</p> <p>Screening and treatment for medical conditions:</p> <p>HIV, VDRL, syndromic RTI, syndromic TB, Hepatitis B (HbsAg), hypo- and hyper-thyroidism (TSH) assessment at first contact</p> <p>Urine routine and microscopic examination and asymptomatic bacteriuria by urine culture four times</p> <p>Gestational diabetes by oral glucose tolerance test thrice</p> <p>Pregnancy induced hypertension (blood pressure) at every visit</p> <p>Anemia (hemoglobin) four times</p> <p>Tetanus toxoid immunization</p> <p>Calcium (1000 mg) and vitamin D (400 IU) supplementation daily starting from second trimester throughout pregnancy</p> <p>Anti-helminthics (Albendazole 400 mg) at 20 weeks</p>	

<p>NUTRITION</p> <p>Counselling</p> <p>IFA (100 mg iron, 500 µg folic acid) supplementation daily throughout pregnancy from second trimester</p> <p>Multiple micronutrients* daily throughout pregnancy</p> <p>Food Supplements</p> <p>BMI <25 kg/m²</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Second trimester: Food supplements (210 kcal, 2 g protein) in the form of a choice of snacks prepared locally and milk (70 Kcal, 6 g protein)[†] - Third trimester: Food supplements (400 kcal, 21 g protein) in the form of a choice of snacks prepared locally and milk (70 Kcal, 6 g protein)[†] <p>Extra snacks (500 kcal, 20 g protein) throughout pregnancy, to women with BMI <18.5 kg/m²</p> <p>BMI 25 to <30 kg/m²</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Milk (70 kcal, 6 g protein) 6 days a week[†] <p>No food supplements to overweight and obese women (BMI ≥ 25 kg/m²)</p> <p>Anemia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Severe anemia (hemoglobin <7 g/dL): Refer to hospital for treatment - Mild to moderate anemia (hemoglobin 7 to 10.99 g/dL): treatment with IFA (100 mg iron, 500 µg folic acid) twice daily <p>Gestational weight gain</p> <p>Weight monitoring every month; identification of inadequate weight gain (IWG) according to Institute of Medicine's guidelines</p> <p>Management of inadequate weight gain (IWG):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutritional Counselling - Hot meal (500 Kcal, 20 g protein) 6 days a week till delivery - Screening and treatment of infections (UTI, RTI, TB) 	<p>Routine antenatal care</p>
<p>WaSH</p> <p>Provision of water filters, hand washing stations, water storage bottles, soap and disinfectants and counselling</p>	
<p>PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT</p> <p>Screen for depressive symptoms using PHQ-9 questionnaire</p> <p>Counselling by study psychologist if PHQ score ≥ 10. Refer to psychiatrist if PHQ-9 score ≥ 15 and/or suicidal ideation.</p> <p>Promotion of positive thinking and problem-solving skills</p> <p>Screen for substance abuse and exposure to second-hand smoke and alcohol use in husbands and counsel</p>	

*Composition given at the end

[†]Observed intake

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EARLY CHILDHOOD

0-6 months: Mothers

Intervention group	Control Group [†]
<p>HEALTH Facilitate hospital visit at 6 weeks postpartum and encourage compliance to supplements.</p>	<p>Routine postnatal and early childhood care</p>
<p>NUTRITION Locally-prepared snacks daily and milk[†] 6 days a week (600 kcal, 20 g protein). IFA (100 mg iron, 500 µg folic acid), Calcium (1000 mg) and vitamin D (400 IU) supplementation daily Multiple micronutrients daily*</p>	
<p>WaSH Continuation of all the WaSH interventions provided during pregnancy (water filters, water storage bottles, hand washing station, soap and disinfectants) and counselling on handwashing and hygiene practices (bathing the infant regularly, keeping the infant's surroundings clean, safe disposal of infant's feces, and handwashing before handling the baby).</p>	
<p>PSYCHOSOCIAL CARE Promotion of positive thinking and problem-solving skills Screening mothers for depressive symptoms and management as required Counselling by study psychologist if PHQ score ≥ 10. Referral to psychiatrist if PHQ-9 score ≥ 15 and/or suicidal ideation.</p>	

*Composition given at the end

[†]Observed intake

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0-6 months: Infants

Intervention group	Control Group†
<p>NUTRITION</p> <p>Initiation of breastfeeding (BF) within the first hour of birth.</p> <p>Early lactation counselling for all mothers to prevent BF problems, resolution anytime during the first 6 months.</p> <p>Counsel on exclusive BF till 6 months of age emphasizing exclusivity of BF from 3 upto 6 months of age.</p> <p>Growth monitoring and management of IWG</p> <p>Weight measurement on day 14 and thereafter monthly to identify IWG (<15th centile as per WHO Growth Velocity Standards, i.e. weight gain <20 g/day between ages day 14 to month 2; <15 g/d for months 3 and 4; <10 g/d for months 5 to 6) for all term infants. Management through: lactation counselling, screening and treatment of infections, facility based management of IWG by senior paediatrician at Safdarjung Hospital after 15 days of continued efforts of lactation support and nomedical cause is identified</p> <p>Additional support for LBW babies and preterm babies (even if not LBW). BF support by lactation counselling through home visits in the first three months (biweekly in first month, weekly in second and third month, monthly from fourth to sixth month).</p> <p>Offer expressed breastmilk feeding for preterm babies only after a breastfeed.</p> <p>Extended support for preterms (through assessment of feeding, growth and investigations within 4-6 weeks after birth) after discharge and ensuring that the advice given at the hospital is followed at home.</p> <p>Support kangaroo mother care at home</p> <p>Vitamin D 400 IU daily for all infants up to 6 months</p> <p>Iron supplementation up to 6 months: VLBW from 2 weeks, LBW from 6 weeks</p>	<p>Routine postnatal and early childhood care</p>
<p>HEALTH</p> <p>Educating mother and other family members to identify danger signs and in early care seeking for illness.</p> <p>Facilitating referral to health facility for infants with any danger signs or illness requiring facility-based management.</p> <p>Counselling on timely immunisation</p>	
<p>PSYCHOSOCIAL CARE</p> <p>Counselling, demonstration and practice sessions for mothers at each home visit on early child play and responsive care.</p> <p>Identification of delayed development and timely referral for further management</p>	

Electronic monitoring system for tracking infants with problems to support them for achieving intervention compliance across all domains.

6-24 months: Children

Intervention group	Control [#]
<p>NUTRITION</p> <p>Effective counselling on initiation of complementary feeding by preparing the mother and family 1-2 weeks prior to 6 months of infant's age</p> <p>Initiation of complementary feeding at 6 months of age and teaching the mother by demonstrations on how to prepare foods at home which can be fed easily to the child 6</p>	<p>Routine early childhood care</p>
<p>months onwards.</p> <p>Provision of daily food supplement with 125 kcal, 2.5 g protein up to 12 months and 250 kcal energy and 5 g protein from 12 to 24 months that includes 80 to 100% RDA of micronutrients</p> <p>Counselling for intake of home-based food</p> <p>Counselling and demonstration of responsive feeding to mother and family members IFA (10 mg iron and 100 mcg folic acid) supplementation daily up to 24 months Lactation counselling for supporting continued BF till 24 months of age</p> <p>Growth monitoring (weight and length monthly); management of IWG (<25th centile as per WHO Growth Velocity Standards) by providing additional food supplements in form of snacks (125 kcal and 2.5 g protein up to 12 months, and 250 kcal energy and 5 g protein from 12 to 24 months) till child has adequate weight gain for 2 consecutive months; nutritional counselling; screening and treatment of infections</p> <p>Home based management of moderate acute malnutrition through counselling, on preparation of augmented home-based foods.</p> <p>Facilitating facility-based management of severe acute malnutrition.</p>	
<p>HEALTH</p> <p>Educating mother and other family members to identify danger signs, and in early care seeking.</p> <p>Facilitating medical management.</p> <p>Counselling on feeding the child during and after illness.</p> <p>Counselling on timely immunization</p> <p>Provision of Albendazole (200 mg) for deworming starting 12 months of age and then 6 monthly</p>	
<p>WaSH</p> <p>Continuation of all the WaSH interventions provided during pregnancy (water filters, water storage bottles, hand washing stations, soap, disinfectants) and counselling on hygiene practices (safe preparation of food, storage and feeding of the child utilizing clean utensils and clean water for cooking and drinking).</p> <p>Clean play area for children; provide play mat. Safe disposal of child's faeces; provide potty.</p>	

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<p>PSYCHOSOCIAL</p> <p>SUPPORT CHILDREN</p> <p>Counselling on early child development.</p> <p>Demonstration and practice session for mother at each home visit on early child play and responsive care.</p> <p>Identification of delayed development three-monthly or as response to parental concerns and timely referral to developmental psychologist.</p> <p>MOTHERS</p> <p>Promotion of positive thinking and problem-solving skills.</p> <p>Screening mothers for depressive symptoms. Counselling by study psychologist if PHQ score \geq 10. Referral to psychiatrist if PHQ-9 score \geq 15 and/or suicidal ideation.</p>	
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Electronic monitoring system for tracking children and mothers with problems to support them for achieving intervention compliance across all domains.

*National Programs for women of reproductive age, pregnant women and under twos (Table S2)

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Supplementary Table 3: Interaction between groups that received preconception or pregnancy interventions compared with those that did not receive these interventions

BMI Z Score at 24 Months	No Pre-conception Intervention (Mean ± SD)		Pre-conception Intervention (Mean ± SD)		Measure of Interaction (95% CI)
No Pregnancy Intervention	-0.95 (1.05)	Ref †	-0.96 (0.97)	0.29 (0.15, 0.43) P=0.0001	0.02 (-0.82, 0.22); P=0.8362
Pregnancy Intervention	-0.77 (1.09)	0.18 (0.001, 0.35); P=0.0476	-0.69 (1.10)	0.27 (0.11, 0.43) P=0.0001	

† Reference group for comparison.

CI: Confidence Interval.

Supplementary Figure 1: Comparison of Mean BMIz scores at 24 Months: Impact of A) Pre-conception Interventions B) Pregnancy Interventions and early child interventions C) Pre-conception and Pregnancy Interventions and early child interventions

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Supplementary Table 4. Body composition parameters at one month of age (Complete Case Analysis)

Variables¹	A	B	C	D
N	112	95	113	98
Fat free mass, kg	3.34 (0.45)	3.26 (0.45)	3.34 (0.42)	3.23 (0.47)
Fat mass, kg	0.54 (0.27)	0.58 (0.23)	0.57 (0.26)	0.55 (0.27)
% Fat Mass	13.74 (6.01)	14.87 (5.43)	14.44 (5.89)	14.47 (6.47)

¹ done only in a subsample.

Values are presented as Mean \pm SD for observed (non-imputed) data

Supplementary Information

Missing Data Handling

We have missing data for Fat-Free Mass (FFM), Fat Mass (FM), and percentage Fat Mass (%FM) in 182 cases due to field-related issues, such as delays in saliva sample collection or mixing of baseline samples with post dose samples. We assumed a Missing at Random (MAR) mechanism, where the likelihood of missingness depends on observed data rather than unobserved data.

The `mi` command in Stata was used to fill in missing values in multiple variables iteratively through chained equations (MICE), which apply a sequence of univariate imputation methods with fully conditional specification (FCS) of prediction equations(1). FCS, which is similar to the Gibbs sampling algorithm (2, 3), allowed us to address each variable with missing values conditionally. To assess the convergence of the multiple imputation process, we examined the stationarity of each chain using *middiagplots* in Stata—plots showing distribution summaries (means, standard deviations) of imputed values against iteration numbers.

The linear regression imputation method (`regress`) was used to impute the continuous variables FFM, FM and %FM. The incorporating predictors such as maternal BMI, child's sex, age in days, and the group to which the child belongs to variables were used as complete predictors (independent variables). 20 imputed datasets were generated and the final results are based on pooled estimates, which were calculated using Rubin's rules(4). This approach combines within- and between-imputation variability, providing more reliable and robust estimates.

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